

Potential Antitubercular Drugs. Part I. Synthesis of Derivatives of Myristic and Stearic Acids**

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The preparation and characterisation of few α -aryloxy, α -thioaryloxy and α -aryl-sulphonyl derivatives of myristic and stearic acids are described. Their antitubercular activity are also reported.

It has been reported by various workers that some derivatives of higher fatty acids exhibit antitubercular activity. Such activity has been demonstrated by Pethe¹ in some derivatives of heptanoic acid. Even the soaps of fatty acids derived from hydnocarpus oil show tuberculostatic properties². Some saturated fatty acids exhibit similar activity^{3,4}.

In view of activity exhibited by derivatives of fatty acids, it was of some interest to prepare a few derivatives of myristic and stearic acids and to study their anti-tubercular activity.

Myristic and stearic acids (I) were subjected to Hell-Volhard-Zelinsky process and the intermediate (II) was treated *in situ* with ethanol, when the α -Bromoesters (III) were obtained. These esters were allowed to react with the different sodium aryloxides and sodium thioaryloxides when corresponding aryloxyesters (IV, X = O) and thioaryloxyesters (IV, X = S) were obtained. These esters were converted *in situ* to the corresponding acids (V) on hydrolysis. Some α -thioaryloxy acids were also oxidised to the corresponding sulphones (VI). A number of hydrazides (VII) were also prepared from the esters (IV)

The compounds prepared have been listed in Table-1.

Bacteriological screening

The *in vitro* tuberculostatic screening of the compounds was carried out in Youman's liquid medium at pH7. *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H37RV *Var hominis* was used as test organism at drug dilutions of 400, 100 and 10 m.c.g./ml. The tubes were incubated at 37° for 28 days prior to inoculation of the drug. The minimum inhibitory concentrations are presented in Table-1. Isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INH) and *p*-aminosalicylic acid (PAS) were the standards used for comparison.

Experimental

All m. p. s. are uncorrected and were taken in sulphuric acid bath.

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA AND BIOLOGICAL SCREENING RESULTS OF α -SUBSTITUTED STEARIC AND MYRISTIC ACIDS

Sl. No.	Acid* @	Yield %	m.p. or b.p.	Mol. Formula	Minimum inhibitory concentration (mcg/ml)
Stearic acid					
1.	α -Phenoxy ^a	75	84	C ₂₄ H ₄₀ O ₂	400.00
2.	α -2-Chlorophenoxy	49	75	C ₂₄ H ₃₉ O ₂ Cl	10.00
3.	α -4-Chlorophenoxy ^b	57	87	C ₂₄ H ₃₉ O ₂ Cl	100.00
4.	α -2, 4-Dichlorophenoxy ^c	63	79	C ₂₄ H ₃₈ O ₂ Cl ₂	100.00
5.	α -2-Methylphenoxy	50	65	C ₂₅ H ₄₂ O ₂	100.00
6.	α -3-Methylphenoxy	53	68	C ₂₅ H ₄₂ O ₂	100.00
7.	α -4-Methylphenoxy ^d	62	66	C ₂₅ H ₄₂ O ₂	10.00
8.	α -4-Methoxyphenoxy ^e	59	170/9mm	C ₂₅ H ₄₂ O ₄	—
9.	α -Thiophenoxy ^f	57	180-2/9mm	C ₂₄ H ₄₀ O ₂ S	—
10.	α -2-Chlorothiophenoxy ^g	58	162/8mm	C ₂₄ H ₃₉ O ₂ SCl	—
11.	α -4-Chlorothiophenoxy	51	66	C ₂₄ H ₃₉ O ₂ SCl	—
12.	α -4-Methylthiophenoxy ^h	83	170-2/5mm	C ₂₅ H ₄₂ O ₂ S	—
13.	α -4-Methoxythiophenoxy ⁱ	79	180-5/8mm	C ₂₅ H ₄₂ O ₄ S	—
14.	α -Phenylsulphonyl	13	86	C ₂₄ H ₄₀ O ₄ S	100.00
15.	α - <i>p</i> -Chlorophenylsulphonyl	62	80	C ₂₄ H ₃₉ O ₄ SCl	100.00
16.	α - <i>p</i> -Methylphenylsulphonyl	40	81	C ₂₅ H ₄₂ O ₄ S	400.00
17.	α - <i>p</i> -Methoxyphenylsulphonyl	7	78	C ₂₅ H ₄₂ O ₆ S	100.00
Myristic acid					
18.	α -Phenoxy ^j	86	76	C ₂₀ H ₃₂ O ₂	100.00
19.	α -4-Chlorophenoxy ^k	75	73-4	C ₂₀ H ₃₁ O ₂ Cl	100.00
20.	α -2, 4-Dichlorophenoxy	62	68	C ₂₀ H ₃₀ O ₂ Cl ₂	10.00
21.	α -2-Methylphenoxy	73	63-4	C ₂₁ H ₃₄ O ₂	10.00
22.	α -3-Methylphenoxy	74	79	C ₂₁ H ₃₄ O ₂	10.00
23.	α -4-Methylphenoxy ^l	64	68	C ₂₁ H ₃₄ O ₂	10.00
24.	α -4-Methoxyphenoxy ^m	51	165-7/8mm	C ₂₁ H ₃₄ O ₄	10.00
25.	α -2-Thiophenoxy ⁿ	91	150/8mm	C ₂₀ H ₃₂ O ₂ S	—
26.	α -4-Chlorothiophenoxy	79	58-9	C ₂₀ H ₃₁ O ₂ SCl	—
27.	α -4-Methylthiophenoxy ^o	84	180-2/6mm	C ₂₁ H ₃₄ O ₂ S	—
28.	α -4-Methoxythiophenoxy ^p	33	160-2/8mm	C ₂₁ H ₃₄ O ₄ S	—
29.	α -Phenylsulphonyl	33	81	C ₂₀ H ₃₂ O ₄ S	100.00
30.	α - <i>p</i> -Chlorophenylsulphonyl	52	73	C ₂₀ H ₃₁ O ₄ SCl	10.00
31.	α - <i>p</i> -Methylphenylsulphonyl	52	87	C ₂₁ H ₃₄ O ₄ S	100.00
32.	α - <i>p</i> -Methoxyphenylsulphonyl	9	83-84	C ₂₁ H ₃₄ O ₆ S	10.00

Table—1 (Cond.)

Esters and Hydrazides.

a. Ethylester	b.p. 140-2°/2mm	hydrazide	m.p. 91°
b. Ethylester	b.p. 125-7°/2mm	hydrazide	m.p. 98°
c. Ethylester	b.p. 120-2°/0.5mm	hydrazide	m.p. 95°
d. Ethylester	b.p. 150-2°/2mm	hydrazide	m.p. 86°
e. Ethylester	b.p. 145-7°/9mm	hydrazide	m.p. 97°
f. Ethylester	b.p. 120-1°/7mm	hydrazide	m.p. 86°
g. Ethylester	b.p. 130°/8mm	hydrazide	m.p. 109°
h. Ethylester	b.p. 132°-5°/5mm	hydrazide	m.p. 119°
i. Ethylester	b.p. 145-6°/6mm	hydrazide	m.p. 74°
j. Ethylester	b.p. 137-40°/8mm	hydrazide	m.p. 75°

* Solvents for crystallization : Ethanol—water for 1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 15, 16, 17, 18, 21, 22, 23, 29, 31, and 32.
pet. Ether for 3, 11, 14, 19, 20, 26 and 30.

@ The acids gave satisfactory C and H analysis. Their eqv. wts. were in agreement with the calculated values.

£ The acid was obtained as an oil.

α-Substituted acids : To a solution of sodium ethoxide (Na, 0.033 mole in ethanol 10 ml) the phenol or thiophenol (0.034 mole) was added. After a few minutes the *α*-bromo ester (III) (0.033 mole) was added in small lots with constant shaking. A white precipitate of sodium bromide soon began to separate. The mixture was allowed to stand for some time and then refluxed for about two hours. Thereafter an aqueous ethanolic solution of sodium hydroxide (NaOH, 5.0 gm in 20 ml 50% aq. ethanol) was added and the mixture refluxed for another 3 hours. The alcohol was now distilled off and the residue diluted with water and filtered. The filtrate after acidification was steam distilled to remove excess of phenol and the acids obtained on cooling were purified by crystallization from suitable solvents (Table-1).

Ethyl α-substituted stearate or myristate

To the ethanolic solution of the acid (3.0 gm in 30 ml) sulphuric acid (0.5 ml) was added and the mixture refluxed for 5 hours. The mixture was now cooled and poured over excess of 10% aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution, extracted with ether, ether extract washed with water, dried (CaCl₂) and solvent removed. The esters obtained as oils were purified by distillation under reduced pressure.

α-Substituted stearic and myristic acid hydrazides

A solution of the ester (0.5 gm), hydrazine hydrate (98%, 0.5 gm) in absolute alcohol (10 ml) was refluxed for 4 hours. The solid obtained was recrystallized from ethanol.

α-Aryl sulphonyl stearic and myristic acid

The thiophenoxy acid (0.01 mole) was dissolved in dilute alkali (5 ml; 2*N.* NaOH). To this an aqueous solution of potassium permanganate (2.5 gm in 80 ml), was added in small lots with constant stirring. The second lot was not added until the colour from the first lot had disappeared. This process was repeated. Lastly the mixture was heated on a water bath for 20 minutes, ethanol (5 ml) added, the precipitate of manganese dioxides, filtered and the clear filtrate acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The mixture was now extracted with ether and the ether extract was dried (MgSO₄). The solid obtained by removal of ether was purified by crystallization.

The result of tuberculostatic activity indicated that *α*-aryloxy and *α*-arylsulphonyl stearic and myristic acids possess antitubercular activity. The derivatives of the myristic acid have been found to be more active than

those of stearic acid. All the α -aryloxy myristic acids tested are active in concentrations of 10 mcg/ml except the phenoxy and the *p*-chlorophenoxy derivatives which are effective in concentrations of 100 mcg/ml. It is apparent from the table-1 that all the sulphones possess antitubercular activity *in vitro*. It is observed that the compounds containing the unsubstituted aromatic ring are the least active.

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